

Intergenerational Perspectives on Gender Power and “Serving Beauty”: A Comparison of Mothers' and Daughters' Aesthetic Practices

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Abstract

From an intergenerational perspective, this study compares the practices of mothers and daughters in terms of aesthetic concepts, beauty consumption and body management through qualitative research methods, revealing the gender power relations behind the phenomenon of “beauty service” and its evolution. The study finds that the aesthetic practices of the mother generation are deeply influenced by traditional gender roles and collectivist culture, emphasizing practicality and social etiquette, while the daughter generation shows more subjectivity and diversity, but also faces the pressure of social aesthetic standards, outward appearance and consumerism. In terms of beauty consumption, the mother's generation focuses on cost-effectiveness and practicality, while the daughter's generation tends to be more high-end and diversified, but accompanied by greater economic and psychological burdens. In terms of body management, while the mother generation is oriented towards health and family responsibilities, the daughter generation focuses more on body image and links it to self-identity and social status. The study further suggests that although the daughter generation shows more initiative in aesthetic practices, they are still subject to the invisible discipline of gender power relations, especially in the digital age, where algorithms and the platform economy have reconfigured the hegemony of aesthetics and reduced the discourse of “pleasing one's own self” to the rhetorical tactics of consumerism. This study provides a new perspective for understanding the complexity of gender power relations in the new era, and calls on society to promote pluralistic aesthetic education, guide a healthy consumer culture, and promote the development of female subjectivity.

Keywords: Aesthetic service; cross-generational comparisons; gender power; aesthetic practices

1. Introduction

In contemporary society, women's appearance and body image have increasingly become the focus of public attention. Whether it is the “face value economy” on social media or the ubiquitous beauty advertisements in daily life, a strong signal is being sent: women's appearance is not only related to their personal image, but is also closely related to their social acceptance, career development, and even marriage and family. This social phenomenon has given rise to an emerging concept - “beauty service”, i.e., the pressure and efforts women have to make to meet the social aesthetic standards. From make-up and clothing to medicine and fitness, women often need to invest a lot of time, money and energy in the pursuit of beauty, even sacrificing their health and self-identity in some cases.

However, “beauty service” is not an isolated phenomenon, but is deeply rooted in gender power relations. For a long time, women's bodies and images have been placed under the male gaze as objects to be evaluated and disciplined.

Society's harsh demands on women's appearance essentially reflect the social structure of gender inequality. It is worth noting that as times change, gender power relations are also undergoing subtle changes, and such changes are distinctly reflected in the aesthetic practices of women of different generations. For example, the mother generation may be more inclined to accept traditional aesthetic standards, while the daughter generation faces more complex social pressures while pursuing individualization.

From a cross-generational perspective, this study aims to explore the similarities and differences in aesthetic practices between the mother and daughter generations of women, and to analyze the changes in gender power relations reflected behind these similarities and differences. Specifically, this study attempts to answer the following questions: first, what are the specific differences between mothers' and daughters' generations of women in terms of aesthetic concepts, beauty consumption, and body management? Second, how do these differences reflect changes in gendered power relations in the context of different eras? Third, in the context of "beauty service", how do women of both generations cope with the social pressure to be aesthetically pleasing and find their self-identity in it? By exploring these questions, this study not only hopes to reveal the gender power mechanism behind the phenomenon of "beauty service", but also tries to provide theoretical support and practical insights for the promotion of gender equality and the development of women's subjectivity.

2. Literature Review

As an emerging social phenomenon, "beauty service" has gradually received academic attention in recent years. The term originated as an Internet buzzword, which refers to the efforts and costs that women are forced to pay in order to meet the social standard of beauty. This concept has similarities with the concepts of "Beauty Labor" and "Body Discipline" proposed by Western scholars. In *The Myth of Beauty*, Wolf points out that society's demand for women's appearance is a kind of hidden oppression, and that women "discipline" their bodies to conform to male-dominated aesthetic standards by wearing makeup and going on diets. On this basis, Gimlin further suggests that women's beauty practices are not only personal choices, but also a kind of socialized behavior, reflecting the inequality of gender power relations (Liu, 2022). In recent years, domestic scholars have also begun to pay attention to the phenomenon of "beauty service". According to Miao Dong, "beauty service" is a passive choice of women under the dual role of consumerism and cultural discipline, behind which is the solidification of gender power relations (Dong, 2014). Kunjin Luo points out that "beauty service" is not only a kind of physical practice, but also a kind of emotional labor, and women are under great psychological pressure in the process of pursuing beauty (Lou, 2012).

Gender power relations are at the core of understanding the phenomenon of "beauty service." Foucault's theory of "disciplinary power" suggests that society disciplines individuals through a series of norms and standards, so that they consciously obey the order of power (Dai, 1994). Bartky further points out that the female body is placed under the male gaze and becomes an object to be evaluated and controlled. This power relationship is not only reflected in the society's harsh demands on women's appearance, but also internalized in women's self-perception and behavioral norms. In Chinese society, the influence of gender power relations on women's aesthetic practices is particularly significant. The traditional concept of "a woman's appearance is for her own pleasure" is deeply rooted, and a woman's appearance is regarded as an important manifestation of her social value. As women's appearance has become more and more important, they have become the most important part of their social value (Zhu, 2022). With the rise of women's status, this power relationship has loosened, but still exists in an implicit way. For example, the phenomena of "face value economy" and "appearance anxiety" on social media are the continuation of gender power relations in the new era. Intergenerational research has contributed to the understanding of gender power relations (Ren, 2023).

Intergenerational research provides an important perspective for understanding the changes in women's aesthetic practices. Mannheim's "Generational Theory" points out that different generational groups will form unique values and

behavioral patterns due to the differences in their upbringing and social backgrounds. (Gao, 2019) In terms of women's aesthetic practices, the differences between the mother's generation and the daughter's generation are particularly obvious. The mother generation (usually referred to as women born in the 1960s and 1980s) grew up in a period of social transition, and their aesthetic concepts are deeply influenced by traditional gender roles and collectivist culture. They are more inclined to accept the mainstream aesthetic standards of society and regard appearance as a kind of “social capital” (Ke, 2015). In contrast, the daughter generation (usually referred to as women born in the 1990s and early 2000s) grew up in the era of consumerism and the Internet, and their aesthetic concepts are more diversified and individualized. While pursuing beauty, they also pay more attention to self-expression and subjectivity (Shen, 2021). However, the generational difference does not mean that the daughter generation is completely free from the constraints of “beauty service”. On the contrary, they may face more complex social pressures in their pursuit of individuality. For example, the phenomena of “face value competition” and “outward appearance involution” on social media have made young women more anxious and uneasy in their aesthetic practices. Although existing studies have shown that the daughter generation is not completely free from the constraints of “beauty service”, they may face more complex social pressures in their pursuit of individualization (Wu, 2022).

Although existing studies have made significant progress in defining the concept of “beauty service,” analyzing the impact of gender power relations, and analyzing intergenerational differences, there are still some pressing issues that need to be addressed. First, there is a lack of intergenerational comparative studies, which makes it difficult to fully reveal the complexity of the phenomenon; second, there is insufficient attention paid to the specific forms of female aesthetic practices (e.g., beauty consumption, body management, etc.); and lastly, there is a lack of in-depth exploration of the changes in gendered power relations and their impacts on women's subjectivities. To address these limitations, this study aims to reveal the gender power mechanisms behind the phenomenon of “beauty service” by comparing the aesthetic practices of mothers and daughters, and to provide theoretical support for the promotion of gender equality and the development of female subjectivity.

3. Method

Adopting a qualitative research method combined with an in-depth interview method, this study aims to explore in depth the similarities and differences in aesthetic practices between mothers' and daughters' generations of women and the changes in gender power relations reflected behind them. Purposive sampling method was used to select mothers and daughters of different age groups, occupations and educational backgrounds as the research subjects, and a total of 20 pairs of mothers and daughters (40 in total) were interviewed.

Table 1 Basic Information Sheet for Respondents (Mothers) (n=20)

Demographic characteristics	Number of persons	Proportion (%)
age		
40~45	6	30%
46~50	11	55%
Over 50 years old	3	15%
careers		
Professionals and technicians	5	25%
Public service workers	4	20%

Business and manual workers	3	15%
Housewives	4	20%
Individual workers	4	20%
Educational Background		
Junior High School	5	25%
High School	6	30%
University College and Above	10	45%

The age range of the mothers' generation was 45-60 years old, born in the 1960s-1980s; the age range of the daughters' generation was 18-35 years old, born after the 1990s. The study population covered both urban and rural areas and different socio-economic statuses. The interviews were organized around the themes of aesthetic concepts, beauty consumption, body management, and social pressures. Each interview lasted approximately 20-60 minutes, and the interviews were audio-recorded with the consent of the interviewees and transcribed verbatim afterwards.

In terms of data analysis, this study used Thematic Analysis to analyze the interview data. Thematic Analysis is a systematic approach to qualitative data analysis that can extract meaningful themes and patterns from text. Specific steps include data familiarization, initial coding, theme generation, theme review, and theme naming and definition. Based on the thematic analysis, this study will further conduct a comparative intergenerational analysis to reveal the changes in gender power relations and their impact on women's aesthetic practices by comparing the similarities and differences between mothers' and daughters' generations of women's aesthetic concepts, beauty consumption, and body management.

Table 2 Respondent's (Daughter's) Basic Information Sheet (n=20)

Demographic characteristics	Number of persons	Proportion (%)
(a person's) age		
15~20	12	60%
21~30	7	35%
31~40	1	5%
careers		
Students	18	90%
Business and manual workers	1	5%
Individual workers	1	5%
Educational Background		
High School	1	5%
University College and Above	19	95%

4. Results

Generational differences in aesthetic concepts: from traditional to pluralistic

Through in-depth interviews and participant observation of 20 pairs of mothers and daughters, the study found that the aesthetic concepts of the mother generation are deeply influenced by traditional gender roles and collectivist culture, and that it is generally believed that a woman's appearance is an important part of her “social capital”, which is directly related to her marriage, career and social status, career and social status. For example, interviewee M1 (49 years old, an individual) said, “In our time, if a girl was good-looking, she could marry well and find a job easily.” This perception reflects society's instrumentalization of women's appearance, where women gain access to social resources by conforming to mainstream aesthetic standards. In addition, the aesthetic standards of the mother's generation are relatively homogeneous, focusing mainly on traditional features such as “white, thin, and young”. Interviewee M2 (48 years old, housewife) mentioned, “Girls look good in clothes when they have white skin and a thin body.” This aesthetic concept is highly compatible with the traditional cultural expectation of women to be “gentle and virtuous”. The aesthetic concepts of the mother generation are closely related to traditional gender roles and socio-cultural norms. For example, Feng Han mentions that gender is a socially formed group of characteristics, roles, activities, and responsibilities that reflect the expectations, requirements, and evaluations of society for both genders and gender relations(Han,2012). Dongxiao Li further points out that gender is a product of social construction, which regulates the norms and scope of activities of both sexes' behavior under different historical periods and values(Li,2006). These ideas fit with the aesthetic concepts of the mother generation.

In contrast, the aesthetic concepts of the daughter generation are more diverse and individualized. They are not only concerned with appearance, but also emphasize self-expression and uniqueness. For example, interviewee D1 (23 years old, freelance musician) said, “I don't think beauty is fixed, everyone has their own unique beauty.” This notion reflects the younger generation's reflection on and challenge to traditional aesthetic standards. However, while pursuing individuality, the daughter generation also faces more complex social pressures. The phenomena of “face value economy” and “outward appearance and inward appearance” on social media have made them more anxious in their aesthetic practices. Interviewee D2 (22 years old, graduate student) mentioned, “Everyone in my circle of friends is taking selfies, so if I don't put on make-up or retouch my pictures, I feel I'm not good enough.” This anxiety reflects the continuation of gender power relations in the new era. The aesthetic concepts of the daughter generation, on the other hand, are influenced by modern cultural and social changes. Ying Chu mentions that a distinctive aesthetic generational difference has been formed between contemporary youth and their fathers, which reflects the changes in aesthetic concepts, the reconstruction of the aesthetic environment, and the subtle emotional interaction between the aesthetic subject and the object. This shows that the younger generation pays more attention to individualization and self-expression in their aesthetic concepts(Chu,2023).

The aesthetic concepts of the mother generation are deeply influenced by traditional gender roles and collectivist culture. They regard appearance as a kind of “social capital” and obtain social resources by conforming to mainstream aesthetic standards. This perception reflects the social conditioning of women's bodies, whereby women internalize social norms in order to maintain their gender roles. However, this conception of aesthetics also limits women's subjectivity. In their pursuit of beauty, the mother generation tends to ignore their own needs and feelings, viewing it more as a social responsibility. In contrast, the daughter generation's aesthetic concept is more diversified and personalized, focusing more on their own preferences, and they have formed their own aesthetic discourse by sharing their beauty experiences through social media and online communities. However, while pursuing individualization, the daughter generation still faces the constraints of social aesthetic standards. The phenomena of “face value competition” and “outward appearance involution” on social media will, to a certain extent, change their original aesthetic concepts. (Liu, 2023; Zeng, 2023; Zhou, 2023).

Generational Differences in Beauty Consumption: From Pragmatism to Consumerism

The mothers' generation is relatively conservative in their beauty consumption, focusing mainly on basic skincare and cosmetics. They pay more attention to the practicality and cost-effectiveness of products rather than brands and trends. For example, interviewee M3 (45 years old, career) said, "I usually use some basic skincare products, mainly depending on whether the price and efficacy can meet my daily needs." This consumption behavior reflects the pragmatic tendency of the mother generation in beauty consumption. In addition, the mother generation's beauty consumption is often associated with social etiquette. For example, interviewee M4 (48 years old, civil servant) mentioned, "When attending important occasions, I will put on makeup, which is a sign of respect for others." This perception reflects the social regulation of women's appearance. The beauty consumption behavior of the mother generation is closely related to social norms and family responsibilities. Yan Wang mentions that the language used in advertisements, the portrayal of men and women, and the identities and power of men and women reflected in advertisements all deeply reflect a dominant consciousness of male-centered gender relations. This mainstream consciousness is reflected in the beauty consumption of the mother generation (Wang, 2005).

In contrast, the beauty consumption of the daughter generation is more diversified and high-end. They not only buy skincare and cosmetics, but also venture into medical beauty and fitness. For example, interviewee D3 (21 years old, college student) said, "I have had double eyelid surgery, and some of my friends go to the gym regularly, so I have the same idea myself." This kind of consumption behavior reflects the younger generation's higher pursuit of "beauty". However, the beauty consumption of the daughter generation is also accompanied by greater financial pressure and psychological burden. Interviewee D4 (20 years old, college student) mentioned, "The money I spend on beauty accounts for one-third of my income every month, but if I don't spend it, I feel like I'm lagging behind." This pressure reflects the influence of consumerism on women's aesthetic practices. The daughter generation's beauty consumption, on the other hand, is influenced by modern consumer culture and social media. This indicates that the younger generation pays more attention to personalization and high-end in beauty consumption.

The beauty consumption behavior of the mother generation reflects the dual influence of pragmatism and social etiquette. They pay more attention to the cost-effectiveness and practicality of products rather than brands and trends. There is a trade-off between economic conditions and social norms in their beauty consumption. In addition, the mother generation's beauty consumption is often associated with social etiquette. For example, they wear makeup on important occasions to show respect to others and maintain social order and gender roles through beauty consumption. In contrast, the beauty consumption of the daughter generation is more high-end. They purchase skincare products, cosmetics, and medical aesthetic services to create a desirable body image and link it to self-identity and social status. However, this consumption behavior is also accompanied by greater economic pressure and psychological burden. The daughter generation often needs to invest a lot of time, money and energy in the pursuit of beauty, even sacrificing health and self-identity in some cases. This pressure reflects the exploitation and regulation of the female body by consumerism (Ma, 2022).

Generational differences in body management: from health to image

Interviewee M4 (48 years old, civil servant) said, "I exercise mainly for health, not to look good." This perception reflects the pragmatic attitude of the mother's generation towards body management. The mother generation's body management is more motivated by health and social etiquette. They keep in shape through exercise and other means, but are less likely to pursue an extreme body image. In addition, the mother generation's body management is often associated with family responsibilities. For example, interviewee M6 (56 years old, housewife) mentioned, "I have to do housework every day and I don't have time to dedicate to the gym." This perception reflects the constraints of traditional gender roles on women's body practices. The mother generation's concept of body management is closely related to traditional gender roles and sociocultural norms. Rui Wang mentions that during the evolution of the custom

of “men dominating the outside world and women dominating the inside world” in the late Qing and early Republican period, women's body management was more constrained by family responsibilities and social roles. This is in line with the concept of body management of the mother generation (Wang, 2022).

In contrast, the body management of the daughter generation focuses more on body image and links it to self-identity and social status. For example, respondent D4 (20 years old, college student) stated, “I think a good body image is not only for looking good, but also represents one's self-discipline and taste.” This perception reflects the younger generation's higher demand for body management. However, the daughter generation also faces greater psychological pressure in their pursuit of body image. Interviewee D6 (34 years old, corporate employee) mentioned, “I have to weigh myself every day, and if I'm a pound heavier, I feel like I've failed.” This pressure reflects society's harsh demands on women's bodies. The daughter generation's body management is influenced by modern culture and social media. This indicates that the younger generation pays more attention to self-identity and social status in body management.

In terms of body management, the mother generation's body management is more motivated by health and family responsibilities. They maintain their body shape through dieting and exercise, but are less likely to pursue an extreme body image. They adhere to a pragmatic attitude, and the constraints of traditional gender roles on women's body practices are also reflected in them. As the traditional gender role of household management, women have difficulty in taking care of their own body management while taking care of the family. On the contrary, the daughter generation's body management is more focused on body image. They pursue an ideal body image through fitness, dieting and medical aesthetics and regard it as a symbol of self-discipline and taste. However, in the process of managing their bodies, they are often faced with society's harsh demands on women's bodies, which are also accompanied by more psychological pressure (Ma, 2022) and the gender power of society in the new era is still oppressing women.

Changes in gender power relations: from regulation to self-regulation.

While the aesthetic practices of the mother generation are mostly the result of passive acceptance of social norms, the daughter generation shows more initiative and subjectivity. For example, the daughter generation has gradually developed its own aesthetic discourse by sharing beauty experiences through social media and online communities. However, this initiative is not completely free from the constraints of gender power relations. While pursuing individualization, the daughter generation is still constrained by social aesthetic standards. In addition, the aesthetic standards of the mother's generation are relatively homogeneous, while the daughter's generation shows more diversified and individualized characteristics. This change reflects the progress of society and culture and the elevation of women's status. However, diversified aesthetic standards also bring new challenges. The daughter generation may face more social pressure and anxiety in their pursuit of individualization.

The change of gender power relations is a complex process. Tianxiu Niu, referring to the study of women's political participation in contemporary China under the perspective of gender justice, points out that the dichotomy between the traditional sphere and the public sphere has led to the exclusion of women from political power relations (Niu, 2013). However, in modern society, the relationship between gender equality and inequality has changed. This indicates that women's initiative in aesthetic practice has gradually increased. This indicates that the younger generation shows more initiative and subjectivity in gender power relations.

In terms of changes in gender power relations, the aesthetic practices of the mother generation are more the result of passive acceptance of social norms, while the daughter generation shows more initiative. The daughter generation has developed its own aesthetic discourse by sharing beauty experiences through social media and online communities. However, this initiative is not completely free from gender power relations. While pursuing individualization, the

daughter generation is still constrained by social aesthetic standards, resulting in invisible self-regulation. Compared with the mother generation, the aesthetic standards of the daughter generation are very diversified, but they will face more social pressure and anxiety while pursuing individualization, and they still cannot get rid of the suppression of gender power relations in a short time (Ma, 2022).

Impact on individual women and society.

The mothers' generation takes a more homogeneous approach to aesthetic practice, but is less subject to individual and social pressure and influence, while the daughters' generation, while showing more individualization in their aesthetic practice, also faces greater social pressure. This contradiction reflects women's desire for self-expression in their pursuit of beauty, but also their difficulty in escaping the constraints of social norms. At the social level, the aesthetic practices of the daughter generation reflect the game between gender equality and consumerism. On the one hand, diversified aesthetic standards provide women with more choices and space for expression; on the other hand, consumerism further strengthens gender power relations through the phenomena of “face value economy” and “outward appearance and inward appearance”. This game reveals the complexity of the phenomenon of “beauty service” and its far-reaching impact on individual women and society (Zeng, 2023).

5. Discussion

This study compares the practices of mothers and daughters in terms of aesthetic concepts, beauty consumption and body management from an intergenerational perspective, revealing the gender power relations and changes behind the phenomenon of “beauty service”. Although the younger generation represented by “daughters” shows more subjectivity and diversity in aesthetic practices, they still face constraints of aesthetic standards in the social environment, anxiety about appearance brought about by the “outward appearance and inward appearance”, and the “craze” of consumerism. The study shows that the current situation and the underlying reasons for it are not only the same, but also the same. Research has shown that the current situation and the mechanisms behind it have provoked deep reflection on the part of all of us.

The gap between generations: the aesthetic gap between mothers and daughters.

The aesthetic concepts of mothers' generation are deeply influenced by traditional gender roles and collectivist culture, which generally regard appearance as a kind of “social capital” and gain social resources by conforming to mainstream aesthetic standards. Combined with the reality of Chinese society, the 60s and 80s, when mothers lived in a period of material scarcity and information blockage, coupled with the ideology of “men dominating the outside world and women dominating the inside world”, women were united in their labor, and regarded the men as the “backbone” of major events, and their aesthetics were tilted towards durable and practical, favoring traditional and natural clothing. Their aesthetics also tended to be durable and practical, and they favored traditional and natural clothing. In contrast, the aesthetic concepts of the daughter generation have become more diversified and personalized under the impact of trendy culture, coupled with the deepening of the concept of equality between men and women, and more open-mindedness, the single aesthetic standard of the male “gentle and virtuous” has been shattered, which also reflects the progress of society and culture and the elevation of women's status. However, while the daughter generation pursues individualization, the constraints of social aesthetic standards, the phenomenon of “outward appearance and inward appearance” on social media, and the prevalence of ‘consumerism’ are also hindering their pursuit of free “beauty”. The prevalence of “consumerism” is also hindering their pursuit of free “beauty”. For example, a subculture blogger's social media account always has bad comments of “not doing their job” underneath; some not-so-healthy ideas (“170, 88 pounds, looks fat”) bring public opinion and trigger people's inner anxiety.

In terms of beauty consumption, the mothers' generation's beauty consumption behavior reflects the dual influence of pragmatism and social etiquette, and they pay more attention to the cost-effectiveness and practicality of products. The beauty consumption of the daughter generation, on the other hand, is more diversified and high-end, reflecting the profound influence of consumerism on women's aesthetic practices. However, this consumption behavior is also accompanied by greater economic pressure and psychological burden (Wen, 2012).

In terms of body management, the mother generation's body management is more motivated by health and family responsibilities, and they maintain their body shape through dieting and exercise, but are less likely to pursue extreme body image. The daughter generation, on the other hand, pays more attention to body image and links it to self-identity and social status. This pursuit is accompanied by greater psychological pressure (Wang, 2022).

Theoretical Perspective: Intergenerational Comparison of "Aesthetic Service".

This study reveals the complexity of the phenomenon of "aesthetic service" and its evolutionary trajectory in the digital age through intergenerational comparison. Taking the generation of mothers who grew up in the early years of reform and opening up (1978-2000) as an example, their aesthetic practices show obvious institutionalized characteristics. At that time, the statute of collective life in state-run units, the standardized requirements for the image of workers under the policy of unit-based welfare housing, and the image of "good wife and mother" portrayed by mainstream media such as Popular Cinema built up a figurative gender discipline system. This passive acceptance of aesthetics reached its peak in the 1990s with the "consultant marketing" of cosmetics counters in department stores, where professional BAs (beauty consultants) visualized the ideology of "beauty = morality" as an operable skincare process by means of technologically-advanced talk such as skin testers. It symbolizes the social practice of passively accepting the results of social norms.

In contrast, the generation of daughters growing up in the Web 3.0 era shows a unique aesthetic paradox, showing more initiative and subjectivity. On the surface, the deconstruction of "invalid make-up" by UP masters in the beauty section of B station, the diversified styles under the hashtag #OOTD of Xiaohongshu (including Hanfu, Y2K, etc.), and the self-creation function of Instagram filters seem to have realized the self-innovation of aesthetics. However, a deeper look into the "beauty labor" of Generation Z in social media reveals that the algorithmic recommendation mechanism is reconfiguring the hegemony of aesthetics. The viral dissemination of Shake Yin's "Makeup Change Challenge", the AI facial analysis of the Light Medical Beauty APP, and the virtual makeup trial based on facial recognition technology on e-commerce platforms ostensibly swear to aesthetic freedom, but in essence transform autonomy into a "new field" of data colonization. This new field of data colonization has become an important part of the aesthetic revolution (Zhou, 2022). This kind of "digital self-training" was dramatically presented in the #AntiFacial Anxiety campaign launched by Xiaohongshu in 2023: although users criticized a single aesthetic, they continued to reinforce the value system of supremacy of the face value through the elaborately designed "face comparison charts" and "history of facial evolution".

However, this kind of initiative is not completely free from the constraints of gender power relations. While pursuing individuality, the daughter generation is still constrained by social aesthetic standards, and this self-regulation reflects the continuation of gender power relations in the new era (Xu & Zheng, 2022). The present work is based on the "evolutionary history of looks" and the "comparison charts" of the daughter generation. This study expands the theoretical perspective of gender power relations and reveals the invisibility and complexity of gender power relations in the new era, i.e., while women are superficially empowered, they are under the pressure of more secretive self-circumscription. The platform economy has reshaped gendered body politics through the illusion of "quantifiable beauty" (e.g., skin-quality test scores, body proportion data), reducing the discourse of "self-pleasing" to a rhetorical tactic of consumerism. The platform economy has also been used as a tool to promote the development of a new era of

gendered body politics. (Nie, 2021) This finding provides a new perspective for understanding the matrix of gendered power in the era of Web 3.0, revealing the symbiotic relationship between technological empowerment and digital discipline, as well as the re-establishment of gendered bodies in the intergenerational transmission process (Zhu, 2024).

Examining the Mind: Peaceful Aestheticism and Healthy Consumption.

The study provides practical insights into the promotion of gender equality and the development of women's subjectivity. Society should pay more attention to women's aesthetic practices, encourage women to pursue diversified aesthetic standards, and reduce society's harsh demands on women's appearance. This study also calls for guiding a healthy consumer culture and reducing the negative impact of consumerism on women's aesthetic practices. The government and social organizations should strengthen the regulation of beauty consumption to prevent the spread of the phenomena of “face value economy” and “outward appearance and inward appearance”. Society should pay more attention to women's aesthetic practices, promote diversified aesthetic education through educational institutions and media platforms, and encourage women to break away from traditional precepts and realize their aesthetic autonomy in career development and artistic creation. Enterprises need to establish inclusive workplace environments and reduce the importance of physical appearance, and schools can offer body esteem courses to cultivate cultural self-awareness among young people. To address the phenomenon of alienation in consumer culture, it is recommended that legislation be enacted to regulate medical and beauty advertisements and propaganda, prohibit excessive marketing that creates anxiety about appearance, and support public visual art projects that showcase different ages, body types, and skin colors, so as to break the hegemony of a single aesthetic hegemony constructed by commercial capital. Social organizations can establish a beauty consumption grading and assessment mechanism to provide women with rational decision-making guidelines, and reshape the value identity of health through community workshops.

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